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**EDUCATION IN MONGOLIA, UKRAINE AND GERMANY: A
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS**

Education is one of the priority areas of the domestic policy of any state, as it is one of the main ways of developing a full-fledged personality.

At present, education in Mongolia, as well as in Ukraine, has a complex structure of the European type and includes pre-school education, general secondary education, out-of-school education, vocational education, and higher education. This guarantees a person freedom of choice and makes it possible to get an education in accordance with his desires, mental and professional abilities. Grazhdane will independently choose the form of training: full-time, evening, correspondence or external studies. With the development of information technology, distance education is successfully developing and improving.

Mongolia is the most Europeanized state in East Asia. Since 2008, Mongolia switched to a 12-year school education from the age of 6 (six of them are elementary schools). Ukraine in 2010 returned from a 12-year to 11-year secondary education. When studying at a university in Ukraine after 4-5 years of study, a bachelor's degree is awarded, after an additional two years of study - a master's or specialist's degree; the next stages of education (except postgraduate education and self-education) are postgraduate studies, doctoral studies.

In 1992, Mongolia switched to the appropriation of academic degrees and to the system of evaluating educational institutions on the Anglo-Saxon model of education. Since 1995, the higher educational institutions of Mongolia switched to a two-level training of graduates: after 4-5 years of study, a bachelor's degree is awarded, after another two years of study - a master's degree, and after defending a special dissertation - a doctor's degree. Since 1998, the higher school of Mongolia switched to a credit system. Excellent students of the 1st and 2nd year of Mongolian universities are encouraged by the state, and have the opportunity to continue their studies at universities in Ukraine, Russia, America, Germany and China.

The education system in Germany is three-stage, i.e. consists of elementary, middle and high school. Education in Germany is free for both local residents and international students. True, to study at a university in many lands it is necessary to pay a tax (500 euros per semester), as well as pay a fee for using libraries, travel tickets, etc. A feature of education in Germany is that there are no entrance exams, and foreign applicants, upon admission to a German university, must pass only one

required exam in the German language (DSH-Pruefung). Due to the difference in the educational system (11 years of education in Ukraine, 13 in Germany) students from Ukraine can enter either by completing two university courses in Ukraine, or through special courses at a university college in Germany.

One of the basic principles of organizing higher education in Germany is "academic freedom." Not only German universities themselves are autonomous entities, but each member of the university community is provided with freedom and independence. In Germany there is no rigid system of training without fail. A student of a German university should himself, having chosen a certain specialty and an appropriate curriculum, organize his curriculum and his time in accordance with the general requirements for students in this program. At the end of each semester, the student collects special certificates of those courses and lectures that he attended. In the event that he scored a certain amount, he can apply for the exam. Most students do not fit into the standard period of study. The average length of study at a higher educational institution in Germany is five years.

There are currently 370 higher education institutions in Germany, including 100 universities and approximately 170 technical universities. Most universities are state-owned. The first stage of higher education is the basic cycle (the study of disciplines at this level takes four years) and ends with passing intermediate exams. Successful passing of exams allows you to continue training at the second stage - the main cycle of training, which lasts five semesters and ends with final exams with a diploma. Based on the results of this cycle, a bachelor's degree may be awarded. The third stage of higher education is postgraduate study, the preparation of dissertations for the degree of doctor, which lasts for 2-4 years. Upon successful defense of a dissertation, a doctor's degree is awarded. Since the degrees obtained by university graduates in Germany differ from those accepted in English-speaking countries, it was decided to switch to the British model - bachelor – master — doctor. However, this process is not yet complete. Having received a German diploma, you can continue your education in graduate school or get a job both in Germany and in other countries of the European Union.

According to the recommendations of the Bologna Declaration, it is advisable for each student to spend at least a semester in some other university, preferably a foreign one. Academic mobility is an opportunity for university students to "move" from one university to another in order to exchange experiences, gain those opportunities that for some reason are not available in their own university, overcome national isolation and gain a common European perspective.

The opportunity to study abroad is access to modern educational programs and material resources; the opportunity to communicate with peers from different countries and cultures; multilingualism; demand for graduates.

ОСВІТА В МОНГОЛІЇ, УКРАЇНІ ТА НІМЕЧЧИНІ: ПОРІВНЯЛЬНИЙ АНАЛІЗ

Проведено порівняльний аналіз систем освіти Монголії, України та Німеччини з метою виявлення найбільш пріоритетних і перспективних напрямків у розвитку систем освіти з точки зору студента у полікультурному світі.

***Ключові слова:** система освіти, іноземний студент, академічна мобільність.*

EDUCATION IN MONGOLIA, UKRAINE AND GERMANY: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

A comparative analysis of the educational systems of Mongolia, Ukraine and Germany was carried out in order to identify the most priority and perspective directions in the development of educational systems from the student's point of view in the multicultural world.

***Key words:** education system, foreign student, academic mobility.*